

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE NOVEL-PAMPHLET GENRE

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Abstract

This article analyzes the theoretical and artistic features of the novel-pamphlet genre. Despite the fact that in literary criticism the pamphlet is mainly interpreted as a small-scale satirical genre, the possibilities of its manifestation in the form of a novel are highlighted based on the experience of world literature. The study examines the composition of the novel-pamphlet, plot construction, character system, author's position, and artistic and journalistic nature.

Keywords: novel-pamphlet, pamphlet, novel genre, satire, journalism, artistic thought, plot, composition, character, author's position, sarcasm, irony, Uzbek literature, literary criticism.

In today's literary process, among the many manifestations of the novel genre, such as historical, modern, fantastic, biographical, educational, mystical, religious, adventure, monological and dialogical, the novel-pamphlet can also be recognized as a separate form. An example of this is a series of novel-pamphlets created by the writer Nurali Kabul in recent years. In literary sources, a pamphlet is usually interpreted as a small-volume satirical work aimed at sharply criticizing the negative aspects of a particular person, social class or political event. However, the experience of world literature shows that there are also large-volume works with pamphlet elements, including novel-pamphlets. For example, in English literature, D. Defoe's "The Ottoman English Merchant", J. Swift's "A Glance at the State of Ireland", and in Russian literature, S. Ya. Rozval's "Innocent Works" and I. Shevsov's "Tlya" are among such examples.

These examples confirm that the pamphlet is not limited to a small-volume genre, but can also appear in the form of a novel. Nevertheless, in many scientific sources and literary dictionaries, the compact size of the pamphlet is interpreted as one of its main features. In particular, N. Hotamov and B. Sarimsakov describe the pamphlet as a small satirical work that exposes a certain social system, reality, or the activities of a political organization through sharp satire.

Similarly, in the dictionary of literary terms by D. Kuronov, Z. Mamajonov, and M. Sheraliyeva, the pamphlet is considered a separate genre of journalism, the main task of which is to sharply criticize a specific person or socio-political structure. Scientists include emotional expressiveness, rhetorical appeals, a strong publicistic spirit, aphoristic conclusions, and ironic expressions reaching the level of sarcasm among the stylistic features of this genre. As a result, the pamphlet is distinguished by an overtly critical spirit that serves to directly influence the reader. Thus, although scientific literature has placed more emphasis on the small size of the pamphlet, literary practice shows that it can also be successfully expressed in the form of a novel.

Literary critic Tulkin Kazakbayev notes the closeness of the pamphlet genre to the feuilleton and emphasizes the existence of certain differences between them, but does not give a clear description of these differences. Nevertheless, through a comparative analysis of these two genres, one can observe the predominance of humor and light satire in the feuilleton, and the sharp criticism, bitter laughter and sarcasm in the pamphlet are more strongly manifested. Therefore, the existing definitions given to the pamphlet serve to understand its general essence.

The creation of the pamphlet in poetic, prose or dramatic forms indicates the closeness of this phenomenon to the manifestation as a method of artistic reflection of reality rather than a strict genre boundary. This expands the possibilities of the pamphlet to be expressed in various literary forms.

The dictionary of literary terms compiled by John Anthony Caddon, one of the

prominent representatives of 20th-century literary studies, provides a special explanation of the concept of pamphlet. It notes that the term "pamphlet" was historically widespread in the Middle Ages, usually used in the sense of a soft-cover book or pamphlet. Later, this term was formed in literature as a short work that covered current issues. Authors often used it as a means of expressing political or religious views. This direction was particularly developed in England in the works of Thomas More, Tyndale, Green, Decker, Gerard Whistonley, Milton, Daniel Defoe and John Swift. In France, pamphlets were widespread, especially during the period of socio-political instability in the late 18th and first half of the 19th centuries.

The composition, plot construction, topic selection, language and author's position, which are inherent in the artistic and publicistic nature of the novel-pamphlet, have been at the center of scientific research since ancient times. The ancient thinker Plato also drew attention to the social significance of artistic creation and emphasized that not all events rise to the level of a work of art. In his opinion, the work should have a positive impact on the human psyche and the development of society, especially in the education of the younger generation. From this point of view, the reality chosen for the pamphlet should not be limited to criticism, but should serve to improve the spiritual environment in society, develop social thinking and form a conscious attitude in the reader. Such a task imposes a certain degree of responsibility on all members of society, along with the creator.

Thus, the novel-pamphlet, like other epic genres, has its own compositional structure, plot system, character system, and narrative style. From this perspective, Aristotle's theoretical views on the issues of plot, composition, and character in a work of art also serve as an important methodological basis for understanding the nature of the novel-pamphlet. The thinker pays special attention to the issue of character, emphasizing, first of all, the need for heroes to have a certain goal and internal position. In his opinion, character is manifested when a person's speech and

actions are directed towards a specific goal.

Based on this view, it can be said that the author's position is of particular importance in the novel-pamphlet. Because in this genre, the creator often brings his own views and aesthetic concept to the forefront. As a result, the plot structure, the development of events, and the system of characters are often subordinated to the author's critical attitude and ideological goal. In this case, the author's point of view may take precedence over the internal logic of the plot. It is for this reason that when analyzing a pamphlet, it is necessary to pay special attention to how the narrator and the author's character are manifested through the narrative.

In modern Uzbek literature, the novel-pamphlet genre is most often mentioned in connection with the work of Nurali Kabul. However, the sharp criticism, bitter laughter, and artistic methods aimed at exposing social phenomena inherent in this genre are based on traditions that have long existed in our national literature.

In general, the novel-pamphlet is a genre aimed at artistic criticism of reality, especially problems in social and political life, based on the novelistic mindset. In this process, the creative concept of the writer, the author's speech and individual style occupy a leading place. Also, the satirical means of expression characteristic of the pamphlet - elements of sarcasm, irony and irony - have been manifested in Uzbek classical literature as an important component of ancient artistic traditions.

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